

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, UK**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections data in UK on May 11th, forecasting the evolutions of the new cases and deaths, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://euroid19.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation is over 240,000 cases, with a ratio per 1000 capita of 3.7, while the forecast of the total deaths is over 34,000.

The data of the new cases are still along a plateau but a forecast has been done.

The data of the new deaths, on the contrary, are showing a trend to decrease and a forecast has been performed.

UK COVID19 DATA & FORECAST May 12th, 2020

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● Verhulst forecast of new deaths
● New deaths